

THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the importance of information technologies in the process of teaching students, the technologicalization of education and the improvement of the quality of education, the importance of information systems and information technologies in making the educational process more effective and modern, and in increasing the motivation and interest of students. It is said that it helps and serves to prepare students for modern life.

Keywords: Innovation, critical thinking, scientific outlook, information-communication, motivation, interactive approach, digital resources, intelligence.

It is known that the main goal of modern education is to provide education, to study the individual capabilities of students and students, and to scientifically examine the intellectual, cognitive, emotional, motivational aspects of educational activities. As noted by our countryman, "another important issue that always makes us think is the etiquette, the gait, in a word, the worldview of our youth. Today The Times are changing rapidly. Who makes these changes feel more than everyone else – young people. May young people be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, do not forget about oneself. Let the call to who we are, what kind of generation we are, always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to remain true to their self. What do we achieve this at the expense of? At the expense of upbringing, upbringing and only upbringing," the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan stressed Sh.M.Mirziyoyev.

Today, the issue of the formation of a free citizen's spirituality, a free personality is the most urgent task before us, that is, we need to educate free, competent people who rely on their own strength and capabilities, approach the events and phenomena taking place around them with an independent attitude, and at the same time see personal interests in harmony with the interests of At present, the problem of educating young people in independent creative thinking, developing opportunities for independent thinking, intellectual and creative potential is one of the pressing issues facing the educational system of our republic. Updates in education envisage the formation of a free, active and independent personality through the educational process, which can vividly imagine the student's future, in this regard, consciously react to his own fate and his own person, and develop himself in various activities.

The effective use of Information Technology in the teaching process is very important for students today. They need to understand the importance of advanced technologies and innovations in the development of the economy, while actively participating in the future as a member of the legal-democratic society.

In the educational process, traditional approaches are changing. In a market economy, students must have knowledge and skills that meet the requirements of the Times. This, in turn, requires the use of innovative methods and technologies in education. Information technology is penetrating into all areas of human activity. The application of Information Technology in the educational process creates new opportunities for students. This, in turn, helps to develop their skills of independent thinking, critical thinking and learning News.

The main goal of the educational process is to educate individuals with independent, critical thinking skills. Students must be prepared to learn news, be able to work cooperatively, and be free to communicate. These skills are important for their future activities. Developing education is important for students to develop a scientific worldview. These educational methods not only limit students to acquiring knowledge, but also teach them the necessary techniques for how they can master and apply their knowledge. Cooperation and communication play an important role in the educational process. Students develop their skills by exchanging ideas with each other, solving problems together, and providing mutual assistance. This process also increases their social skills.

The opinions presented about the role of Information Systems and Information Technology in the educational process are very important. They are a key factor in making education more efficient and modern. Information systems provide event and process management capabilities. They include processes for collecting, processing and transmitting information for targeted effects. These processes provide effective management in education.

Information technology is important in the educational process. They carry out the processes of collection, storage, expression and transmission of information using computers and telecommunications. This, in turn, makes the educational process more efficient and convenient. The transfer of information from generation to generation is associated with the importance of educational and educational work. This process, in turn, allows you to preserve knowledge and convey them to new generations. Information and communication technologies are one of the important factors that create motivations in education. A variety of presentations, animations, and interactive materials increase students ' interest in education. This, in turn, reinforces internal motives for acquiring knowledge.

With the development of technology, the presence of only one computer for training using technical means remained sufficient. The functions previously performed by television, video recorder, kinoprojector, diaprojector, etc., were taken over by the computer with success. In addition, the quality of information transmission, storage, imaging has increased significantly.

To date, computer literacy has become an important sign of culture, and in the future it becomes a necessity for everyone wherever, on which plot they work. So it is no doubt that computer work, teaching to use a computer, will become a common job in the closest time.

Tools of modern information technology include: computer, scanner, video camera, LCD projector, interactive e-board, fax modem, telephone, e-mail, multimedia Tools, Internet networks, mobile communication systems, data warehouse management systems, artificial intelligence systems.

Currently, computers are in the educational system mainly in four directions:

- ✓ as an object of study;
- ✓ as technical means of training;
- ✓ in the management of Education;
- ✓ used in scientific and pedagogical research

At the heart of Information Technology Media is a computer.

Informatization creates the necessary conditions for the development of educational processes. This process provides ample opportunities for the technologization of education and helps to improve the quality of Education. Information systems and information technology play an important role in making the educational process more efficient and modern. They help not only transfer knowledge, but also increase motivation and interest in students. The technologization of education, in turn, serves to improve the quality of education and prepare students for modern life. These processes make it possible to apply innovative approaches in the fields of education and training.

Information technology allows you to create an interactive educational environment with multisensory for teachers and students. In this environment, students can gain knowledge through different emotions, such as through vision, hearing, and movement. This makes the teaching process more interesting and effective. While traditional teaching methods are often based on passive knowledge acquisition, Information Technology provides an interactive approach. This, in turn, activates students and helps them to independently acquire their knowledge.

Information technology helps students develop their intellectual and creative abilities. They will be able to use different data sources, solve problems and develop new ideas. This process, in turn, trains students in independent thinking and innovative approaches. Information technology provides an opportunity for students to independently acquire new knowledge. Through the Internet and other digital resources, students can acquire knowledge in accordance with their interests. This, in turn, makes the process of self-development and learning more effective.

Information technology trains students to work with a variety of data sources. This, in turn, develops their analytical thinking skills and forms the skills for analyzing, evaluating and using data.

In conclusion, we can say that information technology plays an important role in making the educational process more efficient and interactive. They activate students, develop their intellectual and creative abilities, create opportunities for independent knowledge and form skills for working with various data sources. These processes help to improve the quality of education and prepare students for modern life.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev "Yoshlar tarbiyasi eng muhim masalalardan" Manba: O'zA Toshkent-2017
2. Rashidova, G, & Soyimnazarov, N. (2023). FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND LIFE CONCEPTS IN THE PSYCHE OF A CHILD. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(5 Part 2), 35–38. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/15374>
3. Sattorova Mahliyo Burxanovna. (2022). TA'LIM JARAYONIDA PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNINI VA AHAMIYATI. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 1(2), 436–440.
4. Ergashevich, Y. S. (2022). KIBERHUUMLARDAN HIMOYALASHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 46-49.
5. Navro'zbek, Soyimnazarov. "ILMIY VA HAYOTIY TUSHUNCHALARNING BOLA PSIXIKASIDA HOSIL BO 'LISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI." *Innovations in Technology and Science Education* 2.12 (2023): 167-161.